

ALUMINIUM CHLORIDE—A NEW REAGENT FOR THE CONDENSATION OF β -KETONIC ESTERS WITH PHENOLS.
PART VII. THE CONDENSATION OF 4-NITRO-RESORCINOL WITH ETHYL ACETOACETATE.

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In continuation of the previous work, 4-nitroresorcinol has been successfully condensed with ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of aluminium chloride. The product has been proved to be 4-methyl-5-hydroxy-6-nitrocoumarin, which has been degraded to the corresponding mono- and dimethoxycinnamic acids. The formation of the 5-hydroxycoumarin derivative shows for the first time that under the experimental conditions, the chelation between the OH and NO₂ groups in 4-nitroresorcinol, leads to a fixation of the double bonds and consequent stabilisation of one of the Kekule forms.

In the previous parts of this series, it is shown that methyl β -resorcyrate, β -resorcylic acid, resacetophenone and similar phenolic compounds condense with ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of aluminium chloride with the formation of otherwise difficultly accessible 5-hydroxycoumarins in good yields (Sethna, Shah and Shah, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 228; Sethua and Shah, *ibid.*, 1938, 1066; Shah and Shah, *ibid.*, 1938, 1424; Deliwala and Shah, *ibid.*, 1939, 1250; *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1941, 13 A, 352). The reactivity in 2-position of the resorcinol nucleus in the formation of the above 5-hydroxycoumarin derivatives is explicable on the view of fixation of double bonds in the benzene nucleus, the chelation between OH and COOR (R=H or Me) or CO·R (R=Me, Et, Ph, etc.) bringing about that state in presence of aluminium chloride (Shah and Shah, *loc. cit.*).

The condensation of 4-nitroresorcinol with ethyl acetoacetate described here has been undertaken to extend the above observations in the case of nitro group.

4-Nitroresorcinol on condensation with ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of aluminium chloride gives a product (m.p. 209-10°) in poor yield. The structure, 5-hydroxy-6-nitro-4-methylcoumarin (I) has been assigned to it on the following grounds: (i) It gives a strong ferric chloride colouration and dissolves in alkali with non-fluorescent yellow colour; (ii) it is found non-identical by direct comparison with 5-hydroxy-8-nitro-4-methylcoumarin obtained by decarboxylation of 5-hydroxy-8-nitro-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid (*This issue*, p. 340); (iii) its non-identity with 7-hydroxy-6-nitro-4-methylcoumarin (II) (Chakravarti and Banerjee, *J. Indian*

Chem. Soc., 1937, 14, 37) as shown by direct comparison ; and (iv) the condensation product has been definitely proved to be a coumarin derivative by converting it into methylated cinnamic acids (III) and (IV) by the modified method of Shah and Shah (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1938, 7, 213).

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

It is generally accepted that the chelation between OH and COMe in resacetophenone and OH and COOMe in methyl β -resorcyate stabilises one of the Kekule forms (Baker and co workers, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1686; 1935, 628. *et seq.*) but in case of 4-nitroresorcinol no definite conclusion seems to have been arrived at on this point (Baker and Lothian, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 276). The formation of 5-hydroxy-6-nitro-4-methylcoumarin in the present condensation shows that chelation between NO₂ and OH in 4-nitroresorcinol under the experimental conditions, leads to a fixation of the double bonds in the benzene nucleus, as shown below, one of the Kekule forms being thus stabilised, and the carbon atom, which is joined to the carbon atom bearing the hydroxyl group by a double bond, being activated.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Condensation of 4-Nitroresorcinol with Ethyl Acetoacetate in presence of Aluminium Chloride: Formation of 5-Hydroxy-6-nitro-4-methylcoumarin (I).—Anhydrous 4-nitroresorcinol (4 g., 1 mol.), and acetoacetic ester (5.2 g., 1.1 mol.) were dissolved in dry nitrobenzene (15 c.c.). Aluminium chloride (E. P. 10.2 g., 3 mols.) in dry nitrobenzene (25 c.c.) was added and the mixture protected from moisture was heated at 110-115° for 1 hour. The mixture was cooled, crushed ice and concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 c.c.) added and nitrobenzene steam-distilled. After removal of nitrobenzene, it was filtered while hot to remove some tarry material and kept in frigidaire. Next day the substance separated in fine needles along with some uncondensed product. The mixture was dissolved in excess of hot water (100 c.c.) and kept in frigidaire for 4-5 hours, when 5-hydroxy-6-nitro-4-methylcoumarin separated in fine lustrous needles; recrystallised from hot water and a drop of concentrated hydrochloric acid, it had m.p. 209-10°, yield 0.2 g. (Found: C, 54.2; H, 3.3; N, 6.2. $C_{10}H_7O_5N$ requires C, 54.3; H, 3.2; N, 6.3 per cent).

It is sparingly soluble in alcohols, benzene, chloroform and 10% sodium hydroxide; it is more soluble in acetone and acetic acid. It gives with alkalis a deep yellow non-fluorescent colour characteristic of a 5-hydroxycoumarin (Collie and Chrystall, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 81, 1804; Dey, *ibid.*, 1915, 107, 1614) and intense violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The above condensation was attempted using dry ether as a solvent but no definite product could be isolated. It may be noted here that the quality of aluminium chloride affects considerably the quality and yield of the condensation product, and that the condensation in small lots (3 to 4 g.) gives correspondingly increased yields than by working with large quantities of 4-nitroresorcinol at a time.

The *methyl ester*, prepared by methyl iodide in presence of acetone and potassium carbonate, crystallised from hot water as clusters of tiny needles, m.p. 132-33°. (Found: C, 56.2; H, 3.6; N, 6.2. $C_{11}H_9O_5N$ requires C, 56.2; H, 3.8; N, 6.0 per cent).

Conversion of 5-Hydroxy-6-nitro-4-methylcoumarin into o-Methoxycinnamic Acids: Formation of 6-Hydroxy-2-methoxy- and 2:6-Dimethoxy-5-nitro- β -methylcinnamic Acids (III and IV).—To the coumarin (0.2 g.) in acetone solution was added dimethyl sulphate (2 c.c.) and the solution treated with sodium hydroxide (10%, 10 c.c.) with continuous shaking and cooling under tap water. More alkali and dimethyl sulphate (2 c.c.) were added with shaking and the mixture distinctly alkaline left overnight. It was filtered, acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether,

The acid crystallised from hot water and a drop of concentrated hydrochloric acid, m.p. 162-63° (efferv.). It gives violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride and dissolves in sodium bicarbonate solution with effervescence. (Found : C, 50·8 ; H, 4·9. $C_{11}H_{11}O_6N$, $\frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires C, 50·4 ; H, 5·0 per cent).

If the above conversion is carried out at the temperature of water-bath using more dimethyl sulphate (7 c.c.) and stronger alkali (20%), 2 : 6-dimethoxy - 5 - nitro - β - methylcinnamic acid is obtained, which crystallises from hot water, m.p. 206-8°. It decolourises bromine water and potassium permanganate solution and gives no ferric chloride colour test. (Found : C, 53·6 ; H, 5·1 ; N, 4·9. $C_{13}H_{13}O_6N$ requires C, 53·9 ; H, 4·9 ; N, 5·2 per cent).

All analyses are micro-determinations by Mr. M. R. Patkar, M.Sc. of this Institute.

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